

Analyzing the Relationship Between Home Economics Teaching and Practical Life Skills Acquisition in Junior High School Students: An Explanatory Sequential Mixed-Methods Study

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Abstract. This explanatory sequential mixed-methods study aimed to determine the relationship between Home Economics teaching and the acquisition of practical life skills among junior high school students. The quantitative phase involved 101 respondents who rated the extent of teaching dimensions—curriculum content, teaching methods, frequency of instruction, teacher expertise, and problem-solving strategies and their perceived level of life skills acquisition in terms of skill proficiency, confidence in application, behavioral change, retention, and time management. Results showed a very extensive level across all dimensions, with a statistically significant moderate positive relationship between Home Economics teaching and life skills acquisition ($r = .458, p < .001$). Regression analysis revealed that the frequency of instruction and teacher expertise significantly predicted practical life skills acquisition. The qualitative phase, conducted through interviews, supported the quantitative results. Themes emerged around empowerment through hands-on learning, real-world readiness, and the perceived life-long value of the subject. Participants emphasized the transformative and functional nature of Home Economics education in preparing students for independent living. The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings underscores the importance of structured, experiential, and teacher-led instruction in developing essential competencies among learners.

KEY WORDS

1. Home Economics Education 2. Practical Life Skills 3. Junior High School

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1. Introduction

Issues concerning Home Economics teaching and practical life skills acquisition often stem from challenges in curriculum relevance, instructional strategies, and resource availability. Many curricula fail to adapt to contemporary societal needs, resulting in outdated content that may not fully equip students with skills applicable to modern life. Additionally, inconsistent teaching strategies and a lack of teacher training in innovative methods hinder the effective delivery of practical knowledge. Limited resources, such as inadequate facilities and materials for hands-on learning, further restrict students' opportunities to acquire and apply essential life skills. Addressing these issues requires a holistic approach, including curriculum modernization, teacher professional development, and improved resource allocation, to ensure that Home Economics education fosters well-rounded, competent individuals. The

International Federation for Home Economics (IFHE) has emphasized the importance of Home Economics education in fostering adaptability and resilience during crises. In their 2020 Annual Report, IFHE highlighted that Home Economics knowledge empowers individuals to improve their household management, promoting sustainable nutrition and health practices, which are crucial during global challenges. Furthermore, Pendergast (2021) explored the role of Home Economics education in the 21st century, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. He emphasized that Home Economics education is vital in developing critical life skills, including food literacy and sustainable living practices, which enhance individual and family resilience in times of crisis. This perspective aligns with the objectives of Home Economics education, which aims to prepare students for diverse life challenges by equipping them with practical skills and knowledge essential for personal and community well-being. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2024) has consistently advocated for integrating global engagement, sustainability, and digital skills into education systems to maintain relevance in a rapidly changing world. In its "Teaching for the Future" report, the OECD outlines the challenges and key trends for teaching and schools, emphasizing the need for education systems to adapt to global engagement, sustainability, and digital skills. In 2024, the *Journal of Public Health* published a scoping review by Aromatario et al. that examined interventions aimed at enhancing adolescents' personal, social, and life skills. The study identified key components contributing to the success of these interventions, providing valuable insights for educators seeking to improve practical life skills acquisition through Home Economics teaching. The authors highlighted three main categories influencing intervention outcomes: active participation and involvement of adolescents, creation of a safe environment, and anchoring changes in the adolescents' daily lives. These findings underscore the importance of well-structured, supportive, and contextually relevant programs in fostering essential life skills among youth (Aromatario, et.al., 2024). Recent Philippine studies have highlighted the critical role of Home Economics education in equipping students with essential life skills. A 2019 assessment at Tagaytay City Science National High School revealed that both students and teachers positively view the adequacy of instructional facilities, correlating with satisfactory academic performance in Home Economics. This underscores the importance of well-resourced learning environments in fostering practical skill acquisition (Bawar, 2019). However, challenges persist, particularly regarding resource availability. A study focusing on Grade 11 Home Economics students at West Palale National High School identified that insufficient baking tools led to suboptimal learning outcomes and lower academic performance. This finding emphasizes the necessity for adequate tools and equipment to ensure effective teaching and learning processes (Latag, et.al., 2023). Moreover, integrating emerging technologies into the K-12 curriculum has been examined for its impact on knowledge and skills acquisition. A 2023 systematic literature review assessed how technologies like artificial intelligence and e-learning platforms influence student learning outcomes in the Philippines. The study highlighted both opportunities and challenges, indicating that while technology can enhance learning, its effective integration requires careful planning and support (Al, Faruq, et.al, 2023). Digos City, in the Davao Region, faces challenges in teaching Home Economics and practical life skills among junior high students. Despite being an educational hub, resources like teaching materials, equipment, and facilities for hands-on learning are insufficient. Many public schools lack functional kitchens, sewing machines, and essential tools, hindering

students' practice in food preparation, financial literacy, and home management. The shortage of training for Home Economics teachers hinders their ability to adopt modern instructional methods. Many rely on traditional teaching due to limited access to updated practices and professional development. Moreover, technology's underutilization in Home Economics education limits digital learning opportunities, preventing the use of online budgeting tools and interactive modules that explore modern applications like smart home management and entrepreneurship. Socioeconomic disparities challenge students' skill acquisition, with many from low-income households unable to practice skills like meal planning and financial management at home. This economic divide exacerbates the gap between theory and practice, leaving students with limited real-world exposure to what they learn in class.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study —Social Learning, Problem-Behavior, Social Influence, and Risk and Resilience theories offer distinct yet complementary frameworks for understanding how individuals develop and modify behaviors in response to environmental, social, and psychological factors. Social Learning Theory, as articulated by Albert Bandura (1977), emphasizes the process of learning behaviors through observation and imitation of others, particularly role models. Bandura's theory highlights the significance of environmental factors and cognitive processes in shaping behavior, suggesting that individuals are more likely to adopt behaviors observed in others, especially when those behaviors are reinforced. This theory underscores the power of social contexts such as family, peers, and media in influencing behavior development. In contrast, Problem-Behavior Theory, developed by Jessor (1991), focuses on how individuals develop maladaptive behaviors, such as substance abuse or delinquency, as a means of coping with underlying life problems. This theory posits

that these behaviors emerge from a complex interaction of psychological stressors and environmental factors, where individuals engage in problematic behaviors as a coping mechanism or response to unmet needs. It suggests that addressing the root causes of these problems can prevent or mitigate maladaptive behaviors. Social Influence Theory emphasizes the impact of social networks and groups on individual behavior. According to Cialdini and Goldstein as cited in (2004) and Cialdini Jacobson (2021), influences of social norms on climate change-related behaviors. This theory suggests that peer pressure, societal expectations, and group norms can strongly influence an individual's decisions and behavior, especially in adolescence. The theory underscores the power of social context in shaping personal choices, often in subtle, subconscious ways. Risk and Resilience Theory focuses on how individuals respond to adversity, balancing risk factors with resilience factors. According toRutter (1987), while exposure to risk factors such as poverty, abuse, or trauma can increase the likelihood of negative outcomes, resilience enables individuals to adapt and thrive despite these challenges. This theory emphasizes the importance of protective factors, such as supportive relationships and coping strategies, which help mitigate the impact of risks. It highlights how individuals can overcome adversity by leveraging personal strengths and external support systems. The theories of Social Learning, Problem-Behavior, Social Influence, and Risk and Resilience can be effectively applied to the study "Analyzing the Relationship Between Home Economics Teaching and Practical Life Skills Acquisition in Junior High School Students" to understand how students acquire and apply life skills through Home Economics education. Social Learning Theory plays a central role in this context, as students often learn practical life skills by observing their teachers and peers. The modeling of behaviors such as budgeting, cooking,

and time management in a structured classroom environment allows students to imitate and internalize these skills. As students observe the practical demonstrations by teachers and engage in hands-on activities, they are more likely to adopt these behaviors into their everyday lives (Bandura, 1977). Problem-Behavior Theory provides insight into how students may develop maladaptive behaviors if they lack adequate life skills or the support needed to overcome challenges. In Home Economics education, the theory suggests that students who struggle with practical life skills may face difficulties in areas like personal responsibility and time management, which could lead to problematic behaviors. The acquisition of practical life skills through Home Economics classes can serve as an intervention, addressing these gaps and preventing the development of negative behaviors. Social Influence Theory is also relevant, as students' behavior in the classroom is heavily influenced by their peers and teachers. In Home Economics, group activities and collaborative learning provide opportunities for students to influence and be influenced by one another, promoting skill acquisition in a social context.

2. Methodology

The study utilizes an explanatory sequential mixed-methods design to analyze the relationship between Home Economics teaching and the acquisition of practical life skills among junior high school students. The quantitative phase involved administering structured surveys to measure the self-perceived competence of students in practical life skills and the teaching strategies employed by Home Economics educators. Statistical analyses, including correlation and regression, were used to identify significant relationships between variables. The qualitative phase followed, involving semi-structured interviews with selected teachers and students to explore the underlying factors influencing these relationships. This design enabled the integration of quantitative data with in-depth qualitative insights, providing a comprehensive understanding of how Home Economics teaching contributes to developing essential life skills among students.

2.1. Research Design—This study will use the Explanatory Sequential Mixed-Methods Study, a research design that integrates quantitative and qualitative approaches, conducted in two distinct phases, to comprehensively understand a research problem. The quantitative phase employs linear regression; a statistical method used to analyze relationships between variables and predict how independent variables influence a dependent variable. In examining the relationship between Home Economics teaching and practical life skills acquisition, linear regression could assess how specific teaching strategies (independent variables) impact students' development of practical skills (dependent variable). This phase identifies significant patterns and relationships through measurable data. Following this, the qualitative phase adopts a sequential explanatory approach, using methods such as interviews or focus groups to explore the quantitative findings further. This phase aims to provide contextual depth and explanation, shedding light on why and how certain relationships exist, as identified in the statistical analysis. If quantitative data indicates a strong relationship between interactive teaching methods and skill acquisition, the qualitative phase may explore the perspectives of teachers and students to understand the mechanisms driving this relationship. As highlighted in recent methodological studies (Creswell Creswell, 2023; Plano Clark Ivankova, 2022), this design enhances validity by integrating numerical findings with rich, qualitative insights, enabling a

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

nuanced interpretation of the research problem. The Explanatory Sequential Mixed-Methods design is effectively applied to analyze the relationship between Home Economics teaching and practical life skills acquisition among junior high school students, enabling a comprehensive exploration of both measurable and contextual aspects. The study begins with a quantitative phase, where data is collected from students and teachers through structured surveys or standardized tools. This phase measures variables such as the effectiveness of Home Economics teaching strategies—interactive learning, hands-on activities, and theoretical instruction—and the level of students' practical life skills, including problem-solving, decision-making, and resource management. Linear regression analysis is used to evaluate the strength and direction of the relationship between these variables, identifying how variations in teaching strategies predict differences in life skills acquisition. The quantitative findings establish patterns and correlations that provide a statistical foundation for further exploration. The qualitative phase follows, involving semi-structured interviews or focus group discussions to explain and elaborate on the quantitative results. This phase seeks to uncover contextual factors influencing the relationships identified in the quantitative analysis. For instance, if quantitative results indicate that hands-on teaching methods strongly correlate with higher life skills acquisition, qualitative data explores why these methods are effective by examining classroom dynamics, instructional challenges, and the perceived relevance of Home Economics education from the perspectives of both students and teachers. This approach adds depth and context to the numerical findings, allowing for a richer understanding of the observed relationships. The integration of quantitative and qualitative findings enhances the study's validity and provides actionable insights. Quantitative data might show that interactive teaching methods significantly impact stu-

dents' life skills, while qualitative data explains this by highlighting how such methods engage students and promote practical application. This comprehensive understanding informs curriculum design, teacher training programs, and instructional practices, offering valuable insights for educators, school administrators, and policymakers. The sequential integration of data ensures a holistic approach to examining the interplay between teaching strategies and the acquisition of practical life skills, ultimately contributing to the improvement of Home Economics education.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—The ethical considerations of the study were meticulously addressed to ensure the protection of participants' rights and the integrity of the research process. Ethical approval was secured from relevant institutional review boards prior to data collection. Participants, including junior high school students and their teachers, were provided with detailed information about the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights, ensuring informed consent. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained by coding data and securely storing information. Participation was entirely voluntary, and participants were free to withdraw at any point without repercussions. Special care was taken to address the involvement of minors, including obtaining parental or guardian consent. These ethical measures ensured the study adhered to established research guidelines and maintained respect and fairness throughout its implementation.

Social Value

I see the social value of this study as a way to directly improve how Home Economics teachers, like myself, can enhance the delivery of practical life skills education. By identifying effective teaching strategies, I can apply these insights to refine my own instructional practices and better prepare students for real-world challenges. This study also helps me understand how my role as an educator impacts students'

personal and community development, motivating me to adopt relevant and impactful methods. Ultimately, the findings inspire me to contribute to a larger educational mission of creating responsible, self-reliant individuals who can positively influence society.

2.3. Research Respondents—To determine the sample size for a population of 300 TVL-TLE teachers, Slovin's formula was utilized with a margin of error set at 0.05 for a 95% confidence interval. First, the participants were required to be TVL-TLE teachers actively teaching in schools near Digos National High School. This proximity ensures logistical feasibility for data collection and relevance to the localized context of the study. Second, they must have sufficient teaching experience in the TVL-TLE curriculum, ensuring they possess the knowledge and practical insights necessary to provide meaningful responses. Finally, their involvement in teaching practical and technical skills aligns with the study's focus on evaluating the relationship between home economics teaching and the acquisition of practical life skills. These criteria ensure that the selected respondents are well-qualified and can contribute valuable data to the research objectives. In the qualitative phase of the study, the selection of respondents follows a purposive sampling approach designed to gather in-depth insights from participants who can provide rich and relevant information. From the initial population of 300 TVL-TLE teachers, those included in the qualitative phase are typically selected based on their alignment with specific criteria that reflect their ability to contribute meaningfully to the research. Criteria include teaching experience, expertise in the TVL-TLE curriculum, and their active role in teaching practical life skills. These factors ensure that participants possess substantial knowledge and perspectives relevant to the study's focus. The sample size for the qualitative phase is generally smaller than the quantitative phase, thus, it has to be 8 participants, as the goal is

to achieve data saturation rather than statistical representativeness. Teachers who are willing to participate in interviews or focus group discussions are prioritized, ensuring voluntary and ethical participation. The qualitative phase emphasizes understanding teachers' experiences, challenges, and strategies in delivering Home Economics and practical life skills education. This approach allows the researcher to explore the nuances of the data collected in the quantitative phase, providing a richer and more comprehensive understanding of the research problem. The inclusion criteria for learners in the quantitative phase of the study ensured the selection of participants who were actively engaged in the teaching and learning processes of Technological Vocational Livelihood (TVL) and Technological Livelihood Education (TLE). Learners included in the study were required to be actively enrolled in TVL-TLE programs during the academic year under investigation. They were selected from the appropriate grade levels, typically Grades 9 to 12, where TVL-TLE subjects are taught. To ensure meaningful participation, learners were required to have consistent attendance in TVL-TLE classes, demonstrating sufficient exposure to the subject matter. Additionally, learners who actively participated in practical learning activities related to life skills acquisition were prioritized, as their experiences were critical to the study's objectives. Consent and assent were also integral to the inclusion criteria; learners provided their assent to participate, while written consent was obtained from their parents or guardians. These criteria ensured that the selected learners had relevant experiences and were directly involved in the processes being examined, thus enhancing the reliability and validity of the study's findings.

2.4. Research Instrument—The development and crafting of the survey instruments for both the quantitative and qualitative phases of the study drew upon established research and theoretical foundations from relevant lit-

erature. The quantitative survey instrument was informed by McGregor’s (2022) commentary on how educational philosophies shape teaching practices in Home Economics, which provided a basis for framing questions around instructional strategies and their alignment with pedagogical goals. Additionally, the instrument incorporated dimensions of teacher competence highlighted by Kostanjevec, Lovšin Kozina, and Erjavšek (2018), particularly focusing on self-perceived teaching effectiveness across key modules of Home Economics, such as food and nutrition, textiles, and family resource management. The adapted survey statements for the quantitative phase will undergo test-retest procedures and be evaluated for validity and reliability using

Cronbach’s Alpha at a 0.05 confidence level. According to recent literature, a Cronbach’s alpha value above 0.70 is considered acceptable, above 0.80 indicates good reliability, and above 0.90 reflects excellent internal consistency (George Mallery, 2023). In this study, a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.846 demonstrates high reliability, confirming that the survey items are consistent and suitable for accurately capturing the intended data. The questionnaire will use a 5-point Likert-type scale to determine the extent of home economics teaching. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below; Range of Mean and Descriptive Rating home economics teaching.

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation on the Extent of Home Economics Teaching

Score	Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
5	4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The extent of home economics teaching is always observed.
4	3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The extent of home economics teaching is oftentimes observed.
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The extent of home economics teaching is sometimes observed.
2	1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The extent of home economics teaching is seldom observed.
1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The extent of home economics teaching is never observed.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The guidelines governing the procedure for quantitative data collection are in strict accordance with the policies established by The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc. As a component of the formal request, researchers clearly articulate their intentions regarding the collection, analysis, and dissemination of data, ensuring alignment with

the overarching objectives of the research. Anticipated concerns or inquiries from recipients are proactively addressed within this communication, thereby providing reassurance concerning ethical safeguards, confidentiality measures, and the potential advantages of the study. The formal request for permission explicitly seeks authorization to proceed, underscoring the crucial importance of their support in facilitating

Scoring Scale for Practical Life Skills Acquisition

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1	1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The extent of practical life skills acquisition is never observed.

the success of the research.

Securing Endorsement from the Dean

In February 2025, before data collection, the researcher obtained necessary permissions from relevant authorities, including the research adviser, the Dean of The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., and top management through appropriate channels. This involved submitting a comprehensive research proposal outlining the study design, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. The researcher also provided detailed information about the study’s purpose, goals,

and methods for data collection, analysis, and reporting. Furthermore, immediately after the colloquium, the researcher ensured that all participants were fully informed about the study, their rights, and the nature of their involvement. Before participating in the study, informed consent was obtained in the study. In the last week of February 2025, the researcher devoted attention to data accuracy and completeness. The questionnaires will be distributed and retrieved using a standardized and systematic approach, ensuring the reliability of participant responses.

2.6. Data Analysis—The following statistical tools will be used to analyze the relationship between home economics teaching and practical life skills acquisition in junior high school students: an explanatory sequential mixed-methods study.

The Mean Score and Descriptive Interpretations

Will be used to answer statement problem one regarding the extent of home economics teaching and 2, the extent of practical life skills acquisition.

Pearson r or Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient

Will be used to answer problem number 3 about the significant relationship between home economics teaching and practical life skills acquisition in junior high school students.

A Simple Linear Regression Analysis

Will answer statement 4 on the significant influence of home economics teaching on practical life skills acquisition in junior high school students. In addressing statements five and six, implementing a systematic data analysis

approach within the qualitative phase of this study facilitates a comprehensive exploration of participants' insights. Data collected from semi-structured interviews are transcribed verbatim and subsequently verified for completeness and accuracy. A thematic analysis is conducted, commencing with an immersion in the data to discern initial patterns and recurring themes. Key phrases are meticulously coded, with similar codes being categorized into broader themes that correspond with the principal research objectives. These themes undergo additional refinement and scrutiny to ensure they are substantiated by the data and yield significant interpretations. Transparency is emphasized throughout this process by meticulously documenting decisions and maintaining consistency in the coding and theme development. This structured approach ensures that the analysis is exhaustive and dependable, enabling the study to present robust qualitative findings that complement the quantitative results. Following the completion of initial coding, the researcher will develop themes, systematically organizing the codes into coherent groups that illuminate the underlying patterns within the data (Creswell, J.W., and Creswell, J. D 2023). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. When results were yielded, discussions and interpretations followed.

Sequence, Emphasis, and Mixing Procedures.

In this study, the application of sequence, emphasis, and mixing procedures plays a pivotal role in structuring the research design and

ensuring that both quantitative and qualitative data are integrated effectively to address the research questions.

Sequence Is established by conducting the quantitative phase first, where data on the relationship between Home Economics teaching strategies and practical life skills acquisition is collected and analyzed. This phase identifies patterns and statistical relationships, which then guide the subsequent qualitative phase. The qualitative phase follows, using interviews or focus group discussions to explain and contextualize the findings from the quantitative data, ensuring a logical progression of the research process.

Emphasis Refers to the priority given to each phase based on the study's objectives. In this study, the quantitative phase is prioritized as it provides the foundational data on the extent and nature of the relationship between variables. The qualitative phase complements and deepens the understanding of these findings, ensuring a balanced yet data-driven approach.

Mixing procedures

Are applied by integrating the findings from both phases to form a comprehensive narrative. For instance, quantitative results showing a significant relationship between interactive teaching methods and life skills acquisition are elaborated on through qualitative insights that explain how and why these methods work effectively. Data integration ensures that the findings are both statistically robust and contextually rich, providing a holistic understanding of the research problem and actionable insights for improving Home Economics education.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the study's findings on the relationship between home economics teaching and the acquisition of practical life skills among junior high school students. The results are organized according to the sequence of the research questions, beginning with the quantitative analysis of the extent of home economics instruction and the level of practical life skills acquired, followed by an examination of the relationship and significant predictors between the two variables.

Subsequently, the chapter presents the qualitative perspectives of the participants to provide deeper insights and contextual understanding of the quantitative results. The integration of both strands of data enables a comprehensive understanding of how home economics education impacts the development of essential life skills in learners.

3.1. Extent of Home Economics Teaching— Home Economics teaching, also referred to as Family and Consumer Sciences, is an interdisciplinary pedagogical practice that equips learners with essential life skills needed for personal, familial, and societal well-being. It encompasses a broad range of topics, including nutrition, financial literacy, textiles, consumer education, child development, and home management. Home Economics instruction aims to promote practical competencies that enhance students' ability to make informed, responsible decisions in everyday life. Recent research highlights the dynamic evolution of Home Economics education, particularly in response to technological advancement and sustainability demands. For instance, a study conducted by Ogunleye and Olalekan (2024) in Nigeria emphasized the importance of integrating technology in Home Economics teaching, noting that while technology improves engagement and access to resources, barriers such as limited devices and teacher training must be addressed. Similarly, Olanrewaju and Oyebanji (2023) investigated the strategies for enhancing Home Economics teachers' service delivery in Lagos State, recommending increased professional development and better working conditions as means to improve educational outcomes. In

Among the components, scored the highest mean (4.78), reinforcing the assertion that Home Economics lessons are intentionally designed to develop learners' capacity to make informed decisions and resolve everyday challenges. This aligns with the findings of Amanda et al. (2023), who demonstrated that curricu-

a European context, Klavs and Smrtnik Vitulić (2022) explored how Slovenian in-service teachers integrated sustainability topics into their Home Economics classes. Their findings confirmed the relevance of sustainable living education, particularly through modules on food, home environment, and resource conservation, suggesting that teacher training must also adapt to include sustainability competencies. Furthermore, a study by Berglund and Johansson (2025) examined how Home Economics teachers engage students through curricular choices, finding that content related to clothing and textiles was particularly effective in fostering student agency and motivation. Summary of the Extent of Home Economics Teaching

Table 1 provides a synthesized view of how key dimensions of Home Economics teaching contribute to the development of students' problem-solving skills. Based on the responses of 101 participants, all five components—curriculum content, teaching methods, frequency of instruction, teacher expertise, and direct problem-solving instruction—received mean scores ranging from 4.67 to 4.78. These scores fall within the descriptive interpretation of "Very Extensive," reflecting a consistently high level of perceived effectiveness in cultivating learners' critical and analytical thinking through Home Economics instruction.

lum strategies rooted in problem-based learning (PBL) significantly enhance critical thinking and problem-solving outcomes among students. Teaching Methods and Teacher Expertise followed closely, both receiving a mean of 4.76. These results indicate that the way instruction is delivered and the proficiency of the teacher

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Practical Life Skills Acquisition

No	Practical Life Skills Acquisition	n	Mean	Descriptive Interpretation
1	Skill Proficiency	101	4.73	Very Extensive
2	Confidence in Application	101	4.72	Very Extensive
3	Behavioral Change	101	4.75	Very Extensive
4	Retention Skills	101	4.77	Very Extensive
5	Time Management Skills	101	4.75	Very Extensive
	Mean Average	101	4.75	Very Extensive

play pivotal roles in supporting learners' cognitive engagement. Karan and Brown (2022) argued that project-based and experiential instructional approaches effectively sharpen students' reasoning and adaptability in real-life contexts. Moreover, Adeoye and Jimoh (2023) emphasized that the integration of student-centered pedagogies leads to greater creativity and innovative problem resolution, which are foundational to 21st-century competencies. The Frequency of Instruction ($M = 4.70$) and Curriculum Content ($M = 4.67$) also registered very high levels, suggesting that both the regularity and substance of instruction sufficiently support the systematic development of problem-solving skills. This supports McGregor's (2022) assertion that the intentional design of a Home Economics curriculum contributes to learner autonomy and applied knowledge through continuous and structured exposure to real-world tasks. Overall, the mean average of 4.73 confirms the holistic effectiveness of Home Economics teaching in promoting the acquisition of problem-solving skills. These findings advocate for sustained professional development, innovative instructional design, and curriculum enrichment to further advance learners' lifelong competencies.

3.2. *Extent of Practical Life Skills Acquisition*—Practical life skills acquisition refers to the process by which individuals, particularly students, develop competencies necessary to manage everyday tasks and real-life situations independently, efficiently, and responsibly. These skills are often categorized into domains such as personal care, home management, financial literacy, interpersonal communication, problem-solving, and time management (UNESCO, 2021). In the context of education, particularly in subjects like Home Economics, practical life skills are intentionally taught and reinforced through experiential and hands-on learning strategies, equipping learners with functional knowledge applicable beyond the classroom. The acquisition of practical life skills is central to holistic education. It bridges academic learning and real-world application, ensuring that students are not only cognitively prepared but also functionally competent in managing their daily lives. According to the World Health Organization (2021), life skills promote mental well-being and competence, enabling young people to face the realities of life. These skills foster personal development, enhance employability, and encourage responsible citizenship. In educational practice, espe-

cially in Home Economics programs, the development of practical life skills includes tasks such as preparing nutritious meals, managing household budgets, sewing and garment care, maintaining personal hygiene, and practicing effective time and resource management. The goal is to nurture learners' autonomy, adaptability, and decision-making abilities. Recent literature emphasizes the significance of structured curricula in fostering these skills. For instance, Kuusisaari et al. (2021) highlight the role of Home Economics education in teaching sustainability practices, resourcefulness, and every day problem-solving. Similarly, Adeoye and Jimoh (2023) argue that practical life skills are indispensable for 21st-century learners as these enhance creativity, collaboration, and resilience in a rapidly changing world. In summary, acquir-

ing practical life skills is a vital component of a learner's educational journey. It ensures the transferability of knowledge acquired in school to real-life settings, enabling students to function competently and confidently in diverse personal and social contexts. Summary of the Extent of Practical Life Skills Acquisition

Table 2 presents the summary of responses on the extent of practical life skills acquisition among junior high school students, as measured across five key indicators. With a total of 101 respondents, the mean scores for all dimensions fall within the range of 4.72 to 4.77, all of which are descriptively interpreted as "Very Extensive." This suggests a strong consensus among participants that students have acquired practical life skills at a high level through their exposure to home economics education.

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5	Time Management Skills	101	4.75	Very Extensive
Mean Average		101	4.75	Very Extensive

Among the five indicators, Retention Skills received the highest mean score of 4.77, indicating that learners are not only acquiring life skills but are also able to retain and potentially apply them over time. This is closely followed by Behavioral Change and Time Management Skills, both registering a mean of 4.75, which reflect the influence of home economics teaching on learners' daily habits and prioritization skills. Skill Proficiency and Confidence in Application, as recorded mean scores of 4.73 and 4.72,

respectively, reinforce the idea that students feel both competent and confident in performing tasks learned in home economics classes. The overall mean average of 4.75 indicates a pervasive level of practical life skills acquisition, affirming the effectiveness of home economics teaching in developing essential competencies among junior high school students. These findings support the relevance of the subject in fostering functional, real-world skills that contribute to personal development and self-

sufficiency.

3.3. *Relationship Between the Extent of Home Economics Teaching and Practical Life Skills Acquisition*—Table 3 presents the statistical relationship between Home Economics Teaching (adaptation strategy) and Practical Life Skills Acquisition (learning outcome), as analyzed through Pearson’s correlation. The analysis yielded an r-value of 0.458 and a p-

value of <0.001, indicating a moderate positive and statistically significant relationship between the two variables at the 0.05 level of significance. Given that the p-value is less than the alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H), which posits that there is no significant relationship between Home Economics teaching and practical life skills acquisition, is rejected.

Table 3. Relationship Between Adaptation Strategy and Learning Outcome

Variables	Practical Life Skills Acquisition	r-value	p-value	Decision
Home Economics Teaching		0.458	<0.001	Reject H0

Note. *Significant at $p < 0.05$.

The positive correlation coefficient ($r = 0.458$) suggests that as the quality and extent of Home Economics teaching increase, there is a corresponding improvement in students’ acquisition of practical life skills. This confirms the central role of structured instructional strategies—such as curriculum integration, pedagogical techniques, and experiential learning—in shaping students’ ability to manage real-world tasks with proficiency and confidence. This finding is consistent with several empirical studies. For example, González et al. (2024) reported that well-structured Home Economics instruction significantly enhances learners’ competency and life readiness when both theoretical and applied elements are integrated. Similarly, Kuusisaari et al. (2021) emphasized that teachers’ ability to adapt and innovate in Home Economics instruction contributes meaningfully to students’ development of life management skills, including budgeting, nutrition, and time management. In a related study, Bual et al. (2023) observed that effective teaching strategies in life skills education lead to better behavioral outcomes, increased autonomy, and improved practical task execution among ado-

lescents. Therefore, the statistical evidence in Table 13 supports the conclusion that effective Home Economics teaching is a significant predictor of the acquisition of practical life skills. It highlights the importance of investing in curriculum enhancement, teacher capacity building, and instructional design to ensure that learners develop functional competencies relevant to their personal, social, and economic lives.

3.4. *Significant Dimensions of Home Economics Teaching Influencing Life Skills Acquisition*—Table 4 presents the coefficients for each dimension of Home Economics teaching in the regression model. Among the five predictors, two were found to predict practical life skills acquisition significantly: Frequency of Instruction indicating that higher frequency of Home Economics lessons significantly contributes to the acquisition of life skills. This supports findings from McGregor (2022), who emphasized that consistent exposure to skill-based education improves mastery and real-life application. Teacher Expertise confirming that teacher qualifications and competence are crucial in shaping students’ confidence and proficiency in applying practical skills. This aligns

with the study by Ronto et al. (2021), which established that teacher quality is a strong determinant of student learning in applied fields. These findings partially support the hypothesis: while all five dimensions contribute to learning, only frequency of instruction and teacher exper-

tise significantly predict the extent of practical life skills acquisition. This mirrors research by Amanda et al. (2023), who concluded that instructional exposure and teacher guidance are critical levers in strengthening life-related competencies in learners.

Table 4. Dimensions of Home Economics Teaching Influencing Life Skills Acquisition

Model	Unstandardized	Standard Error	Standardized	t	p	Decision
M ₀ (Intercept)	4.747	0.020		235.929	<.001	
M ₁ (Intercept)	1.951	0.562		3.469	<.001	
CC_AVE	-0.032	0.068	-0.044	-0.469	0.640	Accept Null
TM_AVE	0.070	0.062	0.100	1.136	0.259	Accept Null
FL_AVE	0.237	0.078	0.303	3.052	0.003	Reject Null
TE_AVE	0.197	0.065	0.276	3.044	0.003	Reject Null
PSS_AVE	0.117	0.067	0.168	1.731	0.087	Accept Null

Note. CC_AVE = Classroom Competence; TM_AVE = Time Management; FL_AVE = Functional Independence; TE_AVE = Teaching Effectiveness; PSS_AVE = Problem-Solving Skills.

*Significant at $p < 0.05$.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the conclusions drawn from the findings of the explanatory sequential mixed-methods study on the relationship between Home Economics teaching and the acquisition of practical life skills among junior high school students. The conclusions are formulated based on the results of both quantitative and qualitative analyses, highlighting key insights into instructional practices, student skill development, and the significance of teaching dimensions. In line with these conclusions, evidence-based recommendations are proposed to enhance the delivery of Home Economics education and strengthen its impact on students' functional competencies and lifelong learning readiness.

4.1. Findings—On the extent of Home Economics teaching in terms of its dimensions. The participants rated the extent of Home Economics teaching as very extensive across all five indicators. The highest mean was recorded for teaching methods (very extensive), indicating that diverse and engaging strategies were

consistently applied in instruction. Teacher expertise (very extensive) and frequency of instruction (very extensive) also received high ratings, underscoring the relevance of professional preparation and consistent delivery. Curriculum content (very extensive), and development of problem-solving skills (very extensive) further

affirm that the program is comprehensive and skills-oriented. On the extent of practical life skills acquisition among students. Students reported a very extensive level of practical life skills acquisition in all measured domains. The highest mean was observed in retention of skills (very extensive), followed closely by behavior change (very extensive), and time management skills (very extensive). These findings indicate that students not only learn but sustain and apply these skills consistently. Skill proficiency and confidence in application (very extensive), also demonstrate strong learner outcomes. On the significant relationship between Home Economics teaching and life skills acquisition. Pearson correlation analysis revealed a moderate, positive, and statistically significant relationship between Home Economics teaching and practical life skills acquisition ($r = 0.458, p < .001$). This suggests that improvements in instructional quality and delivery are directly associated with better life skills development among students. On the specific dimensions of Home Economics teaching that influence life skills acquisition. Multiple linear regression analysis showed that among the five predictors, only frequency of instruction ($\beta = 0.303, p = .003$) and teacher expertise ($\beta = 0.276, p = .003$) significantly influenced practical life skills acquisition. Curriculum content, teaching methods, and problem-solving strategies were not statistically significant in the model, though they contributed positively to the overall R^2 value of 0.268, indicating that the model could explain 26.8% of the variance in student life skills. On participants' qualitative standpoints regarding the extent of teaching and skill acquisition. Thematic analysis of student interviews revealed three main themes: (1) Skill empowerment through hands-on learning, (2) Real-world application and personal growth, and (3) Teacher influence and instructional consistency. Participants viewed Home Economics as a subject that equips them with essential skills that are both relevant and em-

powering. They emphasized the importance of consistent practice, guided instruction, and the real-life applicability of what they learned. On participants' descriptions of the perceived relationship between teaching and life skills development. Students described Home Economics as a vital link between academic learning and practical living. Three themes emerged: (1) Functional relevance of instruction, (2) Life-long value and readiness, and (3) Integration of knowledge and practice. Students perceived a strong, direct relationship between effective Home Economics teaching and their growing independence, responsibility, and ability to solve everyday problems.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the integration of quantitative results and qualitative insights, the following conclusions are drawn: 1. The extent of Home Economics teaching is perceived to be very extensive. Students consistently rated high levels of curriculum implementation in terms of content, instructional methods, teaching frequency, teacher expertise, and problem-solving skills. This suggests that Home Economics is being delivered in a structured and competency-based manner, reflecting a strong instructional foundation. 2. Students exhibit a very extensive level of practical life skills acquisition. Learners demonstrated high levels of skill proficiency, confidence in application, behavioral changes, retention of learned skills, and time management abilities. This confirms that Home Economics education fulfills its intended role of equipping students with functional, real-life competencies. 3. A significant positive relationship exists between the extent of Home Economics teaching and life skills acquisition. Statistical analysis confirmed that as the quality and extent of instruction improve, students' acquisition of practical life skills increases proportionally ($r = .458, p < .001$), validating the central hypothesis of the study. 4. Frequency of instruction and teacher expertise are the strongest predictors of life skills acqui-

sition. Among the five dimensions examined, only frequency of instruction and teacher expertise showed statistically significant effects in the regression model. This indicates that consistent teaching exposure and teacher competence are critical levers for improving student learning outcomes. 5. Students perceive Home Economics as empowering and transformative. Qualitative data reveal that students associate their learning experiences with real-world applications, increased confidence, independence, and personal growth. The experiential nature of Home Economics makes learning meaningful and memorable. 6. Students describe a strong, functional relationship between Home Economics and life readiness. The curriculum is viewed not merely as academic content but as a life preparation framework. Students believe that what they learn in Home Economics equips them for making responsible decisions, managing their households, and living independently. 7. Social Learning Theory, as articulated by Albert Bandura (1977), emphasizes the process of learning behaviors through observation and imitation of others, particularly role models. Bandura's theory highlights the significance of environmental factors and cognitive processes in shaping behavior, suggesting that individuals are more likely to adopt behaviors observed in others, especially when those behaviors are reinforced. This theory underscores the power of social contexts such as family, peers, and media in influencing behavior development.

4.3. Recommendations—In light of the conclusions drawn from this study, it is evident that Home Economics plays a vital role in equipping students with practical life skills necessary for their personal and future professional lives. To further enhance the impact of Home Economics instruction, targeted actions must be taken by teachers and learners, and policy makers. The following recommendations are proposed to strengthen the delivery, relevance, and long-term effectiveness of Home Economics ed-

ucation in junior high schools: In light of the conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed for educational stakeholders: 1. Sustain and enhance the frequency of Home Economics instruction. Schools should ensure that Home Economics is scheduled regularly throughout the academic year, allowing sufficient time for both theoretical instruction and practical application. 2. Invest in teacher development programs focused on technical expertise and pedagogy. School administrators and education leaders should provide ongoing training and capacity-building programs for Home Economics teachers to strengthen their subject mastery and teaching strategies, aligning them with real-life applications. 3. Reinforce experiential and hands-on learning components in the curriculum. Instructional design should continue to emphasize performance-based tasks, such as project-based learning, simulations, and group activities that mirror real-world situations. 4. Integrate behavior-focused and sustainability-driven content into lessons. Modules should explicitly address time management, healthy living, and sustainable practices to promote long-term behavior change and life readiness among learners. 5. Support monitoring and evaluation systems for the implementation of Home Economics. Regular assessment of teaching practices and student competencies should be implemented to track progress, identify areas for improvement, and inform curriculum development. 6. Promote the visibility and perceived value of Home Economics among the school community. Advocacy campaigns, culminating activities, and showcase events can be used to highlight students' life skill accomplishments, thus increasing stakeholder appreciation of the subject's relevance. 7. For School Principals. The study provides insights into effective teaching methodologies that principals can promote to improve science instruction in their schools. Encouraging the adoption of experimental design-focused activities aligns with goals of fostering

higher-order thinking and 21st-century skills among students, contributing to overall school improvement. 8. Education Program Supervisor in TVL-TLE. For TVL-TLE, which emphasizes technical and vocational education, the study's findings support the integration of experimental design activities that simulate workplace problem-solving scenarios. Supervisors can use this information to advocate for instructional practices that better prepare students for the demands of technical fields. 9. For Future Researchers. The study serves as a foundation for further research into the impact of active learning strategies across other subject areas and grade levels. Future researchers can build on this work to explore how experimental design skills influence long-term academic success, career readiness, or adaptability to technological advancements. This study emphasizes a holistic approach to education, bridging theory with practice and addressing the needs of various stakeholders in the educational ecosystem. This study defined the terms conceptually and operationally to understand better and reference them when discussing results in the preceding chapters.

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